
OPENNESS IN COLOMBIAN ENGINEERING JOURNALS

A PREPRINT

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ABSTRACT

This document gathers information about the number of published documents in Engineering Colombian journals under CC licenses. It has been prepared as part of the final assignments in the CC Certificate Course.¹

Keywords Creative Commons · Open Access · Scientific articles

1 Introduction

A scientific article is a written document, employed by a scientific community to share advances, ideas, results and discussions about the concerning topics of that community. Articles, as a creative works, are subject to copyrights [1].

Scientific articles get published in scientific journals, which play a significant role in the spread of knowledge. Journals belong in most cases to publishers, which depending on their concerns use different commercial models. We could classify the commercial models into two categories: paywalled and open access. As a result of the corresponding model, publishers choose different licensing options.

According to the Colombian Research and Innovation Council - COLCIENCIAS, currently there are 627 Colombian scientific journals, among them 585 have been recognized but their corresponding institutions [2]. Among them, there are 58 journals on Engineering and Technology ².

This document is aimed to present the amount of Colombian scientific articles, which have been licensed employing a Creative Commons license and highlighting the different used licenses.

2 Engineering Scientific Articles

2.1 Colombian Copyright context

As it was presented in [3], in Colombia the copyright reference frame comprise several laws and decrees that define the national copyright reference frame [4][5][6]. Colombian copyright references frame recognizes moral and related rights. Authors and Publishers are allowed to choose how the creative works are shared and spread, then in Colombia CC licenses are fully recognized by its intellectual property laws.

¹This work is licensed under [CC-BY 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

²Data reported to the author directly by COLCIENCIAS

2.2 Sources

Journals resort to Bibliographic Indexes, Repositories and ranking services to improve the visibility of their publications. In the same way as publisher commercial models, indexing services can also be paywalled or open access. Some of the most reputed and recognized open access indexing services employed in Latin America are:

- Directory of Open Access Journals - DOAJ [7].
- Scientific Electronic Library Online - SciELO [8].
- Red de Revistas Científicas de América Latina y el Caribe, España y Portugal - Redalyc (Latin American, Caribbean, Spaniard and Portuguese Scientific Journal Network) [9].

DOAJ gathers journals checking the editorial policies and transparency practices [10]. In contrast to SciELO and Redalyc, DOAJ does not provide bibliometric data. However, it does provide detailed information about the type of licensing and number of papers published by each journal.

The information presented in this document was taken from DOAJ only.

2.3 Engineering Journals and Articles

The Table 1 shows the Colombian Engineering article collection reported in DOAJ. As mentioned above, there are currently 58 Engineering journals, 39 are listed in DOAJ. Not every journal applies to be listed in DOAJ, and not all listed journals have reported their whole collections; therefore, the results presented in this document are indicative and represent a sample. The column **Documents** of Table 1 shows the total number of documents published by all journals using a specific CC license.

License	Journals	Documents	Percentage
CC-BY	13	3580	40.2%
CC-BY-SA	1	108	1.2%
CC-BY-NC	4	521	5.9%
CC-BY-NC-SA	9	1244	14.0%
CC-BY-ND	1	0	0.0%
CC-BY-NC-ND	11	3446	38.7%
TOTAL	39	8899	

Table 1: Number of journals and total documents

The sample has 67.2% (39/58) of journals. The **Percentages** of Table 1 are calculated from the published documents.

Table 1 shows that all CC licenses are used by the selected samples. It is worth to note that the most open (CC-BY) and least open (CC-BY-NC-ND) licenses are the more frequently employed, reaching a 78.9% of the total sample. The resting 21.1% comprise the remaining four licenses, having a 14% using CC-BY-NC-SA. Figure 1 shows the result too.

3 Conclusions

This document shows that the most frequently employed licenses for the open access published documents are CC-BY and CC-BY-NC-ND, with 40.2% and 38.7% of all documents respectively. Creative Commons licenses are widely spread and employed by Engineering journals, but their openness seems to be divided between the most open and the least open.

References

- [1] Creative Commons, *Creative Commons Certificate for Edutactors and Librarians*, [source](#), 2019
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- [3] Andrés Pavas. Basics of Copyright Law. Second Assignment in the CC Certificate Course. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552443>
- [4] Law 23 of January the 28th of 1982 on Copyright, consulted on 17.3.2019

Figure 1: CC Spectrum[11] and obtained results

- [5] [Law 44 of Feb 5th of 1993 on Copyright](#), consulted on 17.3.2019
- [6] [Decree 1474, July-15-2003 Proclamation of WIPO-WTC-1996, WIPO-WTC-1996](#) consulted on 17.3.2019
- [7] [Directory of Open Access Journals - DOAJ. DOAJ website](#), consulted on 16.3.2019.
- [8] [Scientific Electronic Library Online - SciELO. SciELO website](#), consulted on 16.3.2019.
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- [10] [DOAJ. DOAJ Best practices](#). Consulted on 16.3.2019
- [11] [Shaddim. Original CC license symbols by Creative Commons. source. CC-BY 4.0.](#)